

ENGLISH TEACHERS' STRATEGIES AND STUDENTS' WRITING PERFORMANCE

PSYCHOLOGY AND EDUCATION: A MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL

Volume: 24

Issue 5

Pages: 541-547

Document ID: 2024PEMJ2280

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.13381768

Manuscript Accepted: 08-02-2024

English Teachers' Strategies and Students' Writing Performance

Sarah M. Nemenzo*

For affiliations and correspondence, see the last page.

Abstract

This study aimed to assess the level of writing performance of Maritime freshmen students and teachers' strategies in handling English 1 classes in the College of Maritime Education. The descriptive-correlational analysis method was used in this research. The respondents of the study were the bona fide Maritime freshmen students enrolled in Bachelor of Science in Maritime Transportation, Bachelor of Science in Marine Engineering in the University of the Visayas, and English teachers assigned in the College of Maritime Education handling English 1 classes. The instrument utilized in the study was a researcher made questionnaire. The study revealed that the in the utilization of various teaching strategies in writing skills, the use of graphic organizers got the highest rank, followed by blue printing, and then peer talk. The least as ranked by the faculty were timeline, story starter, and simulation of games. The study further revealed that the Maritime freshmen students' level of writing performance as to vocabulary, 97.01% was identified as poor; 0.25% was identified as excellent, good, and satisfactory; and 2.24% was identified as unsatisfactory. For the level of writing performance as to sentence construction, 25.12% was identified as excellent; 18.41% was identified as very good; 17.91% was identified as good; 18.66% was identified as satisfactory; 8.71% was identified as unsatisfactory; and 11.19% was identified as poor. For the level of writing performance as to paragraph development, 88.31% was identified as poor; 1.24% was identified as good; 5.72% was identified as satisfactory; and 4.73% was identified as unsatisfactory. Nevertheless, the final grade obtained in English 1 classes was 2.7 identified as fair; 8.96% of the respondents' final grade was very good; 38.81% obtained a final grade as good; 41.2% obtained a final grade as fair; and 10.95% obtained a final grade of passed. However, the correlation of writing performance and final grade showed insignificant relationship, hence, all hypotheses were not rejected. The facilitating factors that influenced the teaching of writing skills were teachers' commitment, administration support and student's interest in writing. While the hindering factors were classroom non-conducive for learning, mass admission, lack of administration support, and heavy teaching load. In view of the findings and conclusion of the study, a program design is recommended to enhance the writing performance of maritime freshmen students which is beneficial to both students in the College of Maritime Education and English teachers as well.

Keywords: *teaching strategies, writing performance*

Introduction

Every year, thousands of Filipinos are deployed in various countries around the world. According to the Philippine Statistics Authority (2018), the number of Overseas Filipino Workers (OFWs) who worked abroad from April to September 2017 was estimated at 2.3 million. This number is dominated by seafarers as reported by the Manila Times (2017) that the Philippines is the world's biggest source of seafarers, with about 380,000 Filipinos of the 1.5 million seafarers worldwide. This accounts for the demand for maritime education in the country having established a standard in work ethics and English language capabilities among Filipinos.

English language has been officially proclaimed as the language of the sea in the International Maritime Organization (IMO). Likewise, the International Convention on Standards of Training, Certification and Watch keeping for Seafarers (STCW 1978/1995 Convention and Code) as adopted by the International Safety Management (ISM) Code in order to lessen and eradicate communication errors among seafarers, and to enhance as well the Standard of Maritime Communication Phrases (SMCP) to ensure safety at sea while seafarers are on board. This compels the Maritime English teachers to comply with SMCP in order to avoid miscommunication on board. According to Latvian Maritime Academy (2012) matching the competencies and the global requirement must be given equal attention in acquiring competitive seafarers. They mean the use of relevant syllabi, classroom materials and effective teaching approaches to help students deal with a variety of authentic written and oral texts, which are necessary for further academic and professional growth.

Proficiency in English plays a significant role in the life of seafarers. One of the important skills to possess on board is the ability to express thoughts in writing which is extremely essential in order to facilitate communication smoothly like sending messages, writing reports, carrying the chain of command to maintain safety of life and property at sea. However, it has been observed that writing incident reports, memos, instructions and other forms of written communication is perceived a difficult process for the mariners onboard. This has come to the attention of the researcher, being a Maritime English instructor. Considering that writing competence is as equally important onboard, there is a need to look into the strategies being used by the teachers in teaching writing to maritime students. This issue must be given utmost importance among English language teachers to continue gaining the trust of the international maritime industry. The maritime students who would like to become global mariners must be equipped with the essential skills to perform well in their chosen career.

Writing is a communicative activity that needs to be fostered and developed among learners. Olshtain (2006) as cited by Galigao (2009) states that learners who obtained the skills in writing often prosper in school for it develops the learners' communication tasks such as writing lists, sending messages and other related school activities. There are two components in writing: externally, it demonstrates the writer's thought and delivers a proof of learning; and internally, this is the act of writing that helps the writer to organize and simplify thoughts in order to engage in a higher level of cognitive process, such as analysis and synthesis (Walling, 2006).

However, according to the National Center for Education Statistics, annual reports show that the maritime students' achievement test results in writing have dropped from 497 to 484 in the past 9 years from 2006-2015 (AdvancedWriters.comBlog, 2016) and college students show a decline in writing skills each day because of the rise of social media (Gaille Energy Blog Issue 37, 2016). Hartley and Rababah (2003) as cited by Cabellon (2011) have identified that students' writing skills declined each day because of insufficient knowledge in grammar, vocabulary, spelling, and punctuations. These impede the ability of the students to express themselves freely and accurately. As a college instructor at the University of the Visayas in the College of Arts and Sciences, the researcher has observed in her English classes in the College of Maritime Education that most of the students have difficulty in spelling, capitalization, use of appropriate punctuation marks, constructing correct sentences, insufficient vocabulary words, and expressing their ideas and opinions in written communication clearly. Hence, this study is timely and relevant.

Research Questions

The study aimed to identify the level of writing performance of the Maritime 1st year students of the University of the Visayas in the 2ndst semester of Academic Year 2017-2018. Specifically, the study sought to answer the following questions:

1. What are the various teaching strategies used by the English Teachers in English 1?
2. What is the level of writing performance of the Maritime freshmen students at the University of the Visayas in terms of:
 - 1.1. vocabulary;
 - 1.2. sentence construction; and
 - 1.3. paragraph development?
3. What is the final grade of the Maritime freshmen students in their English 1 classes?
4. Is there a significant relationship in the writing performance of the maritime freshmen students and final grade in English 1?
5. What are the factors that influence the teaching of writing skills?
 - 5.1. facilitating
 - 5.2. Hindering
6. What program design for Maritime freshmen students can be proposed based on the results of the study?

Methodology

This quantitative study employed the descriptive-correlational research design in order to describe the various teaching strategies utilized by English teachers in English 1 through ranking, and the final grade obtained by the maritime freshmen students through cleansing of data and tallying the qualified respondents. This was also correlational for it aimed to verify the formulated hypotheses that refer to the relationship between the maritime freshmen students' level of writing performance as to vocabulary, sentence construction, and paragraph development and the final grade obtained in English 1. However, a qualitative design was also employed by using thematic-content analysis to describe the facilitating and hindering factors that influence the teaching of writing skills.

Results and Discussion

The Various Teaching Strategies

Table 1. *Teaching Strategies Used by English Teachers in English 1*

<i>Teaching Strategies in Writing</i>	<i>T1</i>	<i>T2</i>	<i>T3</i>	<i>T4</i>	<i>T5</i>	<i>T6</i>	<i>Rank</i>
Blue Printing	4	3	4	2	3	2	2
Graphic Organizer	1	2	3	3	2	1	1
Listing (Enumeration)	5	5	2	4	1	6	4
Narrowing Topic (Specific Topic)	6	4	5	1	9	5	5
Peer Talks (Listening through Writing)	3	1	1	5	8	4	3
Picture Utilization (including photograph)	2	6	7	7	7	7	7
Reporter's Formula	7	8	6	6	4	3	6
Simulation of Games (Online Essay)	10	10	10	10	10	10	10
Story Starter (Cloze Passages)	9	9	8	8	5	8	9
Timeline	8	7	9	9	6	9	8

The table shows that of all the teaching strategies utilized by the six teachers in English 1 classes, use of graphic organizer got the highest rank, followed by blue printing and third, peer talks which means that most faculty members prepared to engage in these teaching strategies in their respective classes. Graphic organizers are used to facilitate understanding of concepts of less skilled writers particularly the visual learners. The maritime freshmen students are millennials who mostly visual learners.

Blue printing is used in the prewriting stage to generate ideas and to elicit topics from the students by activating their memories to fuel their writing performance.

Peer Talk is also often used because teachers can acquaint students to speak with their fellow students that help to craft their ideas and topics for writing.

Listing, narrowing topic, reporter's formula and picture utilization were ranked fourth to seventh respectively. These strategies were seldom utilized by the English faculty. These were only used when needed because these were often used in the basic education. On the other hand, the three strategies at the bottom were timeline, story starter, and simulation of games. These were rarely utilized by the faculty handling English 1 classes.

Level of Writing Performance of Maritime Freshmen Students

Table 2.1. Level of Writing Performance as to Vocabulary (n=402)

<i>Performance Level</i>	<i>Descriptors</i>	<i>f</i>	<i>%</i>
90-100 %	Excellent	1	0.25
88- 89 %	Very Good	0	0.00
70-79 %	Good	1	0.25
60-69 %	Satisfactory	1	0.25
50-59 %	Unsatisfactory	9	2.24
0-49 %	Poor	390	97.01
Total		402	100 %

The table summarizes the results of the respondents' level of writing performance as to vocabulary. It shows a very provoking result that 390 maritime freshmen students or 97.01% respondents had poor vocabulary obtaining below 49% in their performance level. This merely implies that the Maritime freshmen students' vocabulary skills belonged to low level performance because their acquisition of the second language was underdeveloped.

Only 9 respondents or 2.24% were identified as unsatisfactory for they obtained 50- 59% in their performance level which means they had not fully developed the skill in vocabulary. However, one respondent or 0.25% was identified as satisfactory who obtained a performance level of 60-69%. This means that the student had quite learned the skill but still needed practice to develop the target language. Another one respondent or 0.25% was identified as good who obtained 70-79% performance level in the vocabulary test results which means he has knowledge but needed more practice to become proficient; and one respondent or 0.25% obtained a 100% rating in the vocabulary test results identified as excellent. This implies that only one maritime freshmen student was able to internalize the target language.

Table 2.2. Level of Writing Performance as to Sentence Construction

<i>Performance Level</i>	<i>Descriptors</i>	<i>f</i>	<i>%</i>
90-100 %	Excellent	101	25.12 %
88- 89 %	Very Good	74	18.41 %
70-79 %	Good	72	17.91 %
60-69 %	Satisfactory	75	18.66 %
50-59 %	Unsatisfactory	35	8.71 %
0-49 %	Poor	45	11.19 %
Total		402	100 %

The table reveals that many of the maritime freshmen students' level of writing performance as to sentence construction was fairly inspiring for they were able to identify if the construction of the sentence was grammatically correct or erroneous. This means Maritime freshmen students were able to learn the pedagogical rules of the English language.

101 respondents or 25.12% were identified as excellent for they obtained a score of 9-10 which is equivalent to 90-100%. This implies that the students were able to acquire skills in the rules of subject-verb agreement and mechanics in writing; 74 respondents or 18.41% were identified as very good for they obtained 80-89% in the test results which means that they were proficient in the target language; 72 respondents or 17.91% were identified as good for they obtained 70-79% performance level which means that the students had learned the rules in language skill but needed more practice to become proficient; 75 respondents or 18.66% were identified as satisfactory for they obtained 60-69% performance level which means that the respondents were at least able to recognize correct sentence construction; 35 respondents or 8.71% were identified as unsatisfactory for they obtained 50-59% performance level which means that the students needed to develop their skill; and 45 respondents or 11.19% were identified as poor for they obtained below 49% performance level which means that the maritime freshmen students were struggling in language skill and they needed to emerge in the target language.

The table 2.3 summarizes the results of the maritime freshmen students' level of writing performance as to paragraph development which is very alarming because 355 were identified as poor. This means that their language skills were undeveloped. Likewise, their vocabulary words were insufficient. This implies that Maritime freshmen students strongly experienced difficulty in paragraph development. The table further reveals that only 5 respondents or 1.24% were identified as good who obtained 70-79% performance

level which means that these maritime students are capable of developing any topic; 23 respondents or 5.72% identified as satisfactory who obtained 60-69% performance level rating which barely means these students are capable of writing but utilizing only the basic structures; and 19 respondents or 4.73% identified as unsatisfactory who obtained 50-59% performance level rating which means students were able to emerge in the language skill but needed enhancement to develop their writing skill.

Table 2.3. *Level of Writing Performance of Maritime Freshmen Students as to Paragraph Development (n=402)*

Performance Level	Descriptors	f	%
90-100 %	Excellent	0	0 %
88- 89 %	Very Good	0	0 %
70-79 %	Good	5	1.24%
60-69 %	Satisfactory	23	5.72 %
50-59 %	Unsatisfactory	19	4.73 %
0-49 %	Poor	355	88.31 %
Total		402	100 %

The Final Grade of Maritime Freshmen Students

Table 3. *The Final Grade of Maritime Freshmen Students*

Final Grade	Descriptor	f	%
1.0	Excellent	0	0 %
1.5-1.1	Superior	0	0 %
2.0-1.6	Very Good	36	8.96 %
2.1-2.5	Good	166	38.81 %
2.6-2.9	Fair	156	41.29 %
3.0	Passed	44	10.95 %
Total		402	100 %
Average Final Grade = 2.7			

The table presents the final grade obtained by Maritime freshmen students in their English 1 classes in the second semester of AY 2017-2018. The table reveals that the average final grade obtained by 402 respondents was 2.7 with a description of fair. The computation of the final grades included class standing (attendance, quizzes, projects, oral recitation, and assignments), and major examinations (prelim, midterm, semi-final, and finals).

36 maritime freshmen students or 8.96% were identified as very good who obtained a final grade of 2.0-1.6 which means that these students had acquired the language skills; 166 respondents or 38.81% were identified as good who obtained a final grade of 2.1-2.5 which means that the students moderately acquired the language skills but need to practice ; 156 respondents or 41.29% were identified as fair who obtained a final grade of 2.6-2.9 which means that these students had a little knowledge of language skill and needed to be developed; and 44 respondents or 10.95% were identified as passed who obtained a final grade of 3.0 which means that these students were capable of developing their language skills.

Testing Relationship Between Writing Performance and Final Grade of Maritime Freshmen Students.

Table 4. *Testing Relationship Between Writing Performance and Final Grade of Maritime Freshmen Students*

Pair of Variables	Computed r	P-value	Remarks
Vocabulary and English Final Grade	0.03ns	.549	Do not reject
Sentence Construction and English Final Grade	0.02ns	.697	Do not reject
Paragraph Development and English Final Grade	0.12ns	.809	Do not reject

at 0.05 level of significance

The table summarizes the results of relationship between the respondents' writing performance and their final grade in English 1. The results of the three pairs of variables were insignificant at 0.05 which means that there was no significant relationship between the respondents' writing performance and their final grade in English 1. Therefore, the hypotheses were not rejected. This implies that the respondents' competency in writing had insignificant bearing on their final grade because the English final grade was composed of class standing (attendance, quizzes, oral recitation, project, assignment, and mastery test) and major examinations (prelim, midterm, semi-finals, and final) while writing performance was composed only of vocabulary, sentence construction, and paragraph development. The English final grade constituted the total academic performance in class.

In relation to the above results, Jean Black in his research study on Performance in English Skills Courses and Overall Academic Achievement, stated that the grades for the spoken English course failed to correlate significantly with the overall average academic performance of the students in class. The pedagogical implication was English course skills comprises of several skills and spoken English course is only one of the English skills courses. The results showed low correlations in the total academic performance. This study has implication on the above test results in the final grade in English 1 and students' writing skills which reveal insignificant correlation.

Factors that influence the teaching of writing skills

Table 5.1. *Thematic-Content Analysis on the Facilitating Factors that influence the Teaching of Writing Skills*

<i>Significant Statements</i>	<i>Extracted Codes</i>	<i>Theme</i>
“Listing of ideas to write about requires good students’ writing ability...requires teachers’ expertise in teaching because the students get confused on choosing from the list...”	Teacher’s expertise is relevant in writing skills.	Teachers’ commitment
“When teachers are committed to their jobs, they can find means to provide materials that help the students improve their writing skills”	Teachers’ Commitment develop students’ skill.	
“Anybody can have teaching experience in other fields, but teaching writing, by actually letting the students learn how to write is catastrophic if one does not know how to let the students start to write.”		
“Graphic organizer is helpful ... the writing process of paragraph is smoothly done if they can see the steps visually... Making of the organizers can take some of the teachers’ time. Hence, it needs commitment to the job.”	Teacher provides time conservation to facilitate learning.	Administration support
“To remedy that problem, administration support is needed... administration support is evident when they allow the teachers to come up with their learning guide that suits the needs of the students.”	Administrative support is significant like audio-Visual classroom installation for students learning.	
“It is better to have well-built classrooms with installed TV or projector to carry on this task.” “The classroom must be comfortable for writing too.”		
“I used motivation to the students to start writing. But for the entire writing activity, it does not help my students to write or develop a paragraph.”	Student’s motivation helps to fuel learning.	Student’s interest
“Teaching strategies are just ways to get them started, but it goes back to the students’ motivation if they want to learn or not.”		

The table reveals that teacher’s commitment, administration support, and students’ interest are the facilitating factors that influence the teaching of writing skills. These were the theme from the extracted codes of the English teachers’ significant statements during the focus group discussion. Teacher’s commitment is an essential factor that helps to facilitate instruction despite of difficulties in teaching writing skills. Hence, teachers find means and ways to improve the learning process. According to research, professional commitment is an attitude that someone has toward his or her job. Her dynamic participation and contribution for the profession improves quality of work and productive results (Janelle Cox, 2009). This means that teachers’ devotion and love for teaching facilitate in developing the learners’ skill. Being a potential teacher is not enough, commitment is the most relevant factor that enables one to produce quality learners.

Administration support was another facilitating factor mentioned by the English teachers. Learning resources and healthy environment must be provided for easy teaching and learning process in writing. Audiovisual classroom, learning guide and comfortable classroom must be evident in the learning process. Methner (2013) cited in his dissertation study on the 21st century educational trend the relevance of administration support in the teaching and learning process. He emphasizes that the way to attain quality education is by providing healthy environment and learning resources. And lastly, students’ interest in writing is a prime factor why they learn writing easily. Based on the statement of one of the faculty, motivation is used to fuel students’ writing but it always goes back to the students if they want to learn or not.

Table 5.2. *Thematic-Content Analysis on the Hindering Factors that influence the Teaching of Writing Skills*

<i>Significant Statements</i>	<i>Extracted Codes</i>	<i>Themes</i>
“It is not easy for the teachers to roam around especially that the temperature of the classroom is hot.”	Hot classroom lessen the learning process.	Classroom unconducive for learning
“...but with the oversize classes of 55 for Maritime, I doubt if a teacher can attend the need of the students.”	It is difficult to accommodate oversize classes.	
“I need to explain first .. students find some difficulty in deciding which topic to write if they have very low writing ability. Their writing tasks are more on maritime industries.”	Students’ difficulty in understanding concepts defeats writing skills.	Students of different levels exhaust the teachers’ energy.
We have to take note that the university exercises mass admission. From the start, we cater to different students ...	Mass Admission is one thing that makes teaching writing becomes difficult.	
“In my case, finding the right picture is a challenge.	Insufficient learning material becomes a barrier in effective teaching.	Lack of administration support.
“This activity can only be done if the materials are provided by the department.”		
“If the structure of the classroom is not sufficient for simulation of games, the strategy is futile.”	Unstructured classroom is insignificant for students’ activity.	
“Just imagine one teacher handles 6-7 classes everyday with 50 students in a class. Their schedule is just fully loaded.”	Overloaded teaching schedule exhausts teachers’ energy.	Heavy teaching load.

The table reveals the hindering factors that influence the teaching of writing skills. These were classrooms unconducive for learning, students of different levels exhaust teacher’s energy, lack of administration support, and heavy teaching load. These were the themes

extracted from the English teachers' significant statements during the focus group discussion.

Unconducive classrooms mean that uncomfortable environment delimits students' learning and teachers' mobility. Students of different levels exhaust teacher's energy refers to classes having different levels of understanding or heterogeneous classes make teaching become a difficult process. Based on the significant statements of the faculty, mass admission and low writing ability make teaching a difficult task. Lack of administration support refers to insufficient learning resources and uncomfortable classroom which leads to poor teaching-learning outcome. Based on the significant statement of the faculty, insufficient classroom structure makes futile the teaching strategies, like the use of simulation of games. Heavy teaching load means fully loaded schedule of teachers that result to ineffectiveness in delivering the lesson.

Conclusions

The table reveals the hindering factors that influence the teaching of writing skills. These were classrooms unconducive for learning, students of different levels exhaust teacher's energy, lack of administration support, and heavy teaching load. These were the themes extracted from the English teachers' significant statements during the focus group discussion.

Unconducive classrooms mean that uncomfortable environment delimits students' learning and teachers' mobility. Students of different levels exhaust teacher's energy refers to classes having different levels of understanding or heterogeneous classes make teaching become a difficult process. Based on the significant statements of the faculty, mass admission and low writing ability make teaching a difficult task. Lack of administration support refers to insufficient learning resources and uncomfortable classroom which leads to poor teaching-learning outcome. Based on the significant statement of the faculty, insufficient classroom structure makes futile the teaching strategies, like the use of simulation of games. Heavy teaching load means fully loaded schedule of teachers that result to ineffectiveness in delivering the lesson.

References

- Black, J. (1991). Performance in English Skills Courses and Over all Academic Achievement. Retrieved July 9, 2018 from <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/EJ441446.pdf>
- Buscemi, V. S. (2002). A reader for developing writers. New York: McGraw Hill Companies, Inc.
- Cabellon, A. B. (2011). The Modular Intervention On Composition Writing (Unpublished Thesis from The University of the Visayas, Cebu City) Retrieved January 16, 2018.
- Cabonilla, H. R. (2015). English Language Proficiency of Senior College Student (Unpublished Thesis from the University of the Visayas, Cebu City) Retrieved January 19, 2018
- Chin, Beverly Ann. (2000). The role of grammar in improving student writing. William H. Sadlier, Inc., Retrieved January 21, 2018 from [people.uwplatt.edu.>-ciesield>graminw](http://people.uwplatt.edu/~ciesield/graminw).
- Farooq, M. S. and Ul-Hassan, M. U. (2012), Opinion of Second Language Learners about Writing Difficulties in English Language. South Asian Studies, A Research Journal of South Asian Studies (Vol. 27, No. 1, January –June pp. 183-184) Available from: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/265561270_Opinion_of_Second_Language_Learners_about_Writing_Difficulties_in_English_Language [accessed Jul 11 2018].
- Freeman & Freeman. (2004). Focused freewriting. Retrieved December 17, 2017 from <http://writing2.richmond.edu/wac/freewrit.html>
- Freeman & Freeman. (2004). Focused freewriting. Retrieved December 17, 2017 from <http://writing2.richmond.edu/wac/freewrit.html>
- Galigao, R. P. (2009). The English Language Competence of Graduating Students of the University of the Visayas: A Training Design (Unpublished Dissertation Paper from the University of the Visayas Cebu, City) Retrieved February 4, 2018.
- Girdharan, B. (2012). Identifying Gaps in Academic Writing of ESL Students. US-China Education Review A 6 (2012) 578-587 Earlier title: Retrieved July 9, 2018 from <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/ED535491.pdf>
- Grafen, G. (1996). Scientific articles, types and organization of texts. Frankfurt/M. Lang.
- Hyland, K. (2003). Genre-based pedagogies: A social response to process. Journal of Second Language Writing, 12, 17-29
- Jacaba, V. (2015). Photo Essay: Structural and Thematic Analyses. (Unpublished Thesis from University of the Visayas, Cebu, City)
- Journal of maritime transport and engineering. (2012). vol. 1, no. 1. Latvian Maritime Academy Research Institute Lithuanian Maritime Academy. Retrieved December 8, 2017 from www.latja.lv/wp-content/uploads/files/ZinatRakstuKrajumi/Publikacija.pdf
- Kalandadze, M. (2007). English academic writing., Europe: CCS
- Krashen, S. (2003). Explorations in language acquisition and use. Portsmouth, NH: Heinemann
- Malouff, J., Rooke, S., et.al.(2018). Simple strategies academics can use to help students improve their writing skills. School of

Behavioural, Cognitive and Social Sciences, University of New England. Retrieved February 10, 2018 from <http://www.une.edu.au/news-and-events>

Methner, G. V. (2013). Perceptions of administrative support and follower readiness in middle school teachers (Dissertation Paper) Retrieved 7-9-2018 from https://etd.ohiolink.edu/rws_etd/document/get/bgsu1383582751/inline

Monitor model. TesoLclass.com. Retrieved Feb.2, 2018 from <http://www.tesolclass.com/applying-sla-theories/monitor-model/>

Pirsl, D. et. al. (2011). Writing skills at university level.

Saddler, B. & Preschern, J. (2014). Improving sentence writing ability through sentence combining practice. Retrieved January 19, 2018 from <http://researchgate.net/publication28799712>

Sahbaz, K. N., & Duran, G. (2001). The efficiency of cluster method in improving creative writing skills of students. Turkey International Journal

Sedita, Joan.,2015. Sentence combining. Literacy Lines. Retrieved February 6, 2018 from <https://keystoliteracy.com/blog/sentence-combining/>

Sentence combining: Teaching rules of sentence structure by doing. Retrieved January 22, 2018 from <http://www.interventioncentral.org/academic-interventions/writing/sentence-combining-teaching-rules-sentence-structure-doing>

STWC guide for seafarers.2010.Retrieved November 3,2017 from www.mptusa.com/STWC_guide_english

Tinig ng marino. (2010). Upgrading of maritime education. Internet Edition 2012. Retrieved November 3,2017 from [http://www.ched.gov.ph/statistics/upgrading of maritime education.](http://www.ched.gov.ph/statistics/upgrading%20of%20maritime%20education)

Tocmo, C. S. (2014). Writing Assessment: A Developing Tool from Existing Instruments (Unpublished Thesis from University of the Visayas, Cebu, City)

Triza, R., Kristiawan, M., Johari, I., & Asvio, N. (2016). The effect of clustering technique towards students writing skills of narrative text in high school 5 Pariaman, West Sumatera. Research Journal of Social Sciences. January 28, 2016. Retrieved February 4, 2018 from Journal home page: <http://www.aensiweb.com/RJSS>.

Weaver, C. (1998). Lessons to Share on Teaching Grammar in Context. Portsmouth, NH: Heinemann.

Affiliations and Corresponding Information

Sarah M. Nemenzo

University of the Visayas – Philippines